

DEVELOPING FUTURE ENGINEERS WITH BROAD VIEWS AND DEEP SKILLS – THE EMERGENCE OF A NEW T²-CAPABILITY PROFILE

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ABSTRACT

Companies are increasingly stressing their need for recruits and employees who can understand the company strategy and operations on a wider scale and with an integrative mindset, as opposed to siloed departments, jobs, and people possessing those jobs.

With new digital technologies, new organizational forms such as team-based organizations and virtual teams as well as Human Resource Management practices like job rotations, there are increasing opportunities for cooperation and integration of people with different backgrounds and skillsets, as the interplay between marketing (business function) and R&D (engineering function).

However, having the company practices and infrastructure "right" for holistic and cross-disciplinary work does not suffice. The professional preparedness of the practitioners has to support this new paradigm as well. The solution has been proposed to be T-shaped capabilities, where the vertical line represents the deep expertise in one area, and the horizontal line overview expertise to better understand processes outside one's domain. This is an improvement to I-shaped capabilities, where the connecting horizontal integration is missing.

The paper propagates for a prospective upgrade to the T-shaped capability model, the T² capability profile. The core idea - derived from interviews with industry managers - is that two horizontal lines differ in scope. The societal/business megatrends demand a set of non-contextual understanding of issues such as sustainability, quality as well as basic technical and financial literacy, and the other horizontal line is made of company-and industry-specific processes. To conclude, the opportunities to foster T²-capabilities in (engineering) education get discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The concept of capability profiles

Capability profiles in the realm of human resource management (HRM) and knowledge management (KM) are not a new issue of discussion and research. The early stages of capability profile discussion were centered around depth (of expertise) vs. width. People were assumed to possess either the vertical capabilities that lead them into a deeper and deeper knowledge of their area of expertise (like a business function like quality management or a branch of science/engineering, such as software engineering or artificial intelligence. This deep yet now wide capability profile (that has reach only in the vertical dimension) got a symbol and name of the I-shaped capability profile. Some people and jobs were claimed to ask more for a horizontal view, i.e. ability to act across business functions and knowledge areas. This integrative capability profile with just horizontal reach was labeled as a “hyphen”(-)-shaped capability profile, also called generalist (vs. specialist). Typically these capabilities were seen to be of demand in the higher ranks of the organization, where the responsibility areas of managers grew to cover multiple business functions.

Lately, the developments arising both from organizational evolution as well as from changes in job markets and younger generations' values about work and careers have risen into discussion the need to re-look at the capabilities needed and achievable. Some proposals have propagated a professional profile standing on two pillars, the so-called π -shaped (Greek letter “pi”) capability profile [1]. The essence of the construct is well visualized in its name carrying the symbol of two vertical expertise and in addition ability to see the organization's processes and linkages between expertise areas (the horizontal bar in π). Logical reasoning for the new profile is the intrusion of technology and digitalization into all corporate functions, so, to act successfully as a digital marketing manager, one must master both the technology (“digital”) and well as its domain of usage (“marketing”). Likewise, a technology developer like a software engineer should understand not only technology (like Artificial Intelligence=AI) but also its intended usage cases and areas, like digital marketing powered by AI.

Another proposed model is the V-shaped professionalism, where the two expertise areas are more permanently intertwined, connected, and even converged. In his 2022 paper [2] Oerther describes the need for this new model as a call for “humanitarian technologists”, who are better equipped to solve complex societal challenges e.g. in areas of sustainability.

1.2 The shift from I- to T-shaped capability profile and its evolutions

The most common depiction of an ideal capability profile for a modern professional is the T-shaped capability profile. The fundamental idea is well readable in the name of the profile: A T-shaped professional has got deep expertise in one area to offer to

the organization, but can also disseminate that knowledge to experts in other domains for common benefit as well as acquire knowledge from other areas. The need for a T-shaped professional has been studied and theorized in many different areas ranging from the medical sphere, entrepreneurship, innovation, and engineering education [3], [4].

Due to the presence of the T-shaped capability profiles in the discourse since the 1990s, it is understandable many modifications and enlargements to the base construct have been proposed. Many of them have focused on adding to the model capabilities parallel to both vertical and horizontal dimensions (Figure 1), stating e.g. how in the vertical reach an individual should possess expertise on more than one domain or system and in the horizontal reach be able to apply that knowledge to more than one context (industrial and/or socio-cultural).

Fig. 1. Example of extensions to the T-shaped capability model [5]

This paper aims at evaluating the models proposed in terms of their relevance to the current and anticipated operating environment of engineering professionals. The paper also proposes a new improvement on the T-shaped capability model and discusses the role Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) can have in the development and supply of the new T²-shaped professional to industries.

2 METHODOLOGY

The paper at hand relies on its arrival to conclusions on various pathways of inquiry. To start with, a brief synthesis of prior research and conceptualization is offered as well as its merits and possible shortcomings get discussed. Secondly, the author utilizes the constructional pathway, where a new model is introduced as derived from logical reasoning that relies on the author's observations of societal, organizational, and technological change. Finally, the identification pathway pre-tests the model with thematic discussion with stakeholders in a) technology-based companies and b) educators in HEIs. The participants in the thematic interviews were selected with purposeful convenience sampling. The experts were chosen to represent both the technology and business point of view – both in the case of the company as well as

HEI participants. The industry stakeholders represented the following industries and positions in them: ICT-development/CEO, Energy Technology/Senior Quality Expert, New Materials/Business Development Director, and Machinery/Chief Financial Officer. The education stakeholders with whom the discussions were held operate in the programs of Logistics Engineering and International Business Management, on top of which the author has done observations when acting within a program of Technology Business and Futures Foresight. The author's dual role as a designer of the model and observer of the reality is a potential bias. However, this selectiveness characteristic of conceptual and interpretative qualitative research is all-natural in the early stages of the development of a framework. In the further stages of validation, further development of the model and its practical instantiations more rigorous methodology, sampling, and implementation will be applied.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Overview and assessment of the prior work on capability profiles

The current discourse on capability profiles strongly propagates widened area of expertise as a plausible characteristic of an employable and successful employee of today and the future. However, the ideas of multiple areas of deep expertise – like in the case of π -shaped and enlarged T-shaped capability profiles contradict the trends of continuing specialization and technological development that force the companies and the professionals in them to focus their efforts to gain a competitive edge. The concept of multiple or boundaryless careers suggests that the Y- and Z-generations will not only change the company they work for multiple times on their career journey or just move up the corporate ladder, but will also make notable horizontal moves and leaps in their career trajectory. This will over time lead to multiple expertise profiles for an individual in some cases where a person moves to a different field of action (e.g., from production to procurement) or from one industry to another (e.g., from consumer electronics to aviation industry). This type of double expertise is however a result of a long career rather than a valid requirement for all let alone young recruits. Likewise, it is not a realistic target for education, since the birth of two or more true expertise areas would mean a substantial lengthening of study times. The societal pressure and demands for education efficiency are pushing the development in the opposite direction.

Furthermore, the capability profile models in hand do not make a claim on the layer in which the “wide” combinatory capabilities should be applicable. In reality, the processes in which one's special areas connect to the expertise of others are context-sensitive, i.e. dependent on the industry or even a specific company where work takes place. Looking at the issue from the engineering angle, the same expertise of software engineering connects to other functions and professions in different ways in the case of medical technology vs. in the e-commerce platforms.

Finally, the models are rather unspecific in what counts as a capability. Also, the concepts of system, culture, and process are quite fuzzy, just like the boundaries between them.

3.2. The new T²-capability model to elaborate on and its implications for HEIs

The findings of the previous work as reviewed in Section 3.1. were based on logical reasoning. The utility of the models proposed in prior literature was mirrored by the other trends and challenges for modern organizations as introduced by research. In the principle of Socratic dialogue, the tensions between the models (thesis) and findings of current and foreseen forces for organizations and jobs (antithesis) in them, a new prospective model combining the findings gets proposed in this paper (synthesis).

The T²-model borrows its name from the main structure of the model, where the reality-bounded view of one true expertise (the vertical line of the letter T) is enriched with two layers of combinatory/generic capabilities (see Figure 2). The horizontal layers differ in two ways: 1) The contextuality of the capability, and 2) The level of expertise required in those layers.

Fig. 2. Structural model of T²-capability profile

The T²-model suggests that the truly relevant combinatory capabilities e.g. in engineering jobs are made of the ability to understand and communicate the connections between one’s expertise and function to other fields of knowledge *within context*. Context refers to the application area and operating environment of the organizational knowledge, that tends to be specific to both industries (“clock speed” of an industry, value/supply chains, the role of standards and regulations, etc.) as well as to companies (different business models within an industry utilize different pieces of knowledge and in different ways). This context-dependent layer that goes for wider understanding does not need the match the depth of the specific professional expertise one possesses.

The upper and more generic, i.e. non-context dependent knowledge is needed for basic understanding of key concepts, their definitions, and relationships. This type of knowledge on issues such as quality, sustainability, etc. serves for one’s ability to

participate in discussions on the subject area and forms a base on which one can deepen the use of this generic knowledge in the context and further into their field and profession.

Based on the discussions with industry experts and engineering education practitioners, the following instantiations of T²-capability profiles for software engineering capabilities as they manifest in two different context domains of digitalization were ideated (Figures 3 and 4) to test the feasibility of the model proposed. The stakeholders in the industry represented differing business functions (quality management, procurement, logistics, strategic management, financial management) just as the higher education stakeholders came both from business and technology faculties (and from different streams in them). Both the context-dependent as well as generic capabilities introduced were sourced from these stakeholders and applied to the framework with a manufacturing company in mind.

Fig. 3. T²-capability profile for software skills in Research and Development

Fig. 2. T²-capability profile for software skills in Marketing

Ironically, higher education institutes (HEIs) have traditionally been well equipped to contribute to both the most generic and most specific capabilities. In the early stage of the studies, learners across domains get introduced in their basic courses to the fundamental principles and key lexicons of multiple domains, after which the move to specialization studies aiming at narrow but deep professional skills takes place. The structure of HEIs divided into faculties, schools, and further study programs reflects

this specialization and siloing of knowledge. Depth and deepness in an inherent nature of top-level research – the other main function of HEIs – but serves badly the needs of the cross-disciplinary nature of the world of work. Furthermore, due to practical issues of scheduling and premises (separated campuses), even the generic skills are often taught in a way that does not bring people (both teachers and students) from different domain areas together.

Hackathons, case competitions, business simulations, and entrepreneurial (when team-based) incubation are some practices that HEIs and even some companies have deployed to foster the “T²-mindset”. However, these events and learning spaces typically involve a limited total student cohort and the ones engaged are often self-selecting themselves to these learning instances due to their T²-mode already existing. For the remaining ones the horizontal, combinatory capability building is left to companies, who promote width of knowledge by trainee and talent onboarding programs and by job rotation. It is worth noticing that the contributing stakeholders from business organizations and education saw both technical and financial “literacies” – basic knowledge in key concepts and processes in the fields of technology and economics – as generic capabilities needed across functional domains and thus attached to the capability profile of any expert. This finding proposes to open up the educational offerings of business and engineering schools to a wider variety of students to enhance future collaboration and shared knowledge within organizations. Likewise, internationalization should be a knowledge possession of each individual in a modern networked world of work.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

To conclude, the new model once deployed by joint planning between HEI departments as well as between HEIs and companies would prepare and motivate the HEI learners better for their careers and add to their job market value and flexibility. In addition, altering the HEI learners early on to the combinatory views and experiences would create benefits for employers by the wider usability and mobility of the workforce, thus increasing resilience to changes in the operating environment and allowing lower (re)training cost of the employees. The author aims to continue the work by creating more industry- and job-specific models and empirically testing the feasibility of the model both in HEI and industry settings.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hayajneh, J. A. M., Elayan, M. B. H., Abdellatif, M. A. M., & Abubakar, A. M. (2022). Impact of business analytics and π-shaped skills on innovative performance: Findings from PLS-SEM and fsQCA. *Technology in Society*, 68, 101914.
- [2] Oerther, D. B. (2021). Humanitarian technologists as prototypical V-shaped professionals. In the *2021 IEEE Global Humanitarian Technology Conference (GHTC)*. pp. 253-257. IEEE.

- [3] Boehm, B. (2018). Education and Social Development of T-Shaped Software Engineers. In *Proceedings of the 4th Annual International Conference on Management, Economics and Social Development*. pp. 745-749.
- [4] Kulkarni, V. A., Dhanvijay, M. R., Bewoor, A., & Malathi, P. (2022). Effectiveness of CO-PSO Formulation and Attainment with a T-shape Engineer for Aligning Students Learning Outcomes with Alumni Profiles. *Journal of Engineering Education Transformations*, 35 (Special Issue 1). pp. 153-159.
- [5] Heikkinen, K.-P. (2018). Exploring studio-based higher education for T-shaped knowledge workers, case LAB studio model. (Doctoral dissertation). University of Oulu, Oulu, Finland.